

Effects of Community Mobilisation Strategies on Implementation of Community Policing in Kenya

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Abstract:- A nation's development depends on the health and productivity of its growing population. The health of the population as well relies on the security of every individual to be able to effectively contribute to national development. The security concern in Kenya has been persistent ever since gaining independence although it has taken different dynamics over the century. The influx of small arms has led to an increase in violent crime especially in the major cities. This is compounded by engagement of the youthful population in criminal activities. The study was guided by the social capital theory. The study aimed at establishing the influence of community mobilization strategies implementation of community policing in Kenya. Successful community policy enhances reduction of crime in the country. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and targeted households within the community. The households were stratified and a sample size of 98 households drawn and participated in the study. A questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. Data was analysed by SPSS version 20 and presented in tables of frequency and percentage. The study found that mobilization strategies can be used to implement community policing in Kenya. The findings indicated that 82% mobilization techniques enhances community policing .This implies that when you increase mobilisation strategy by 1% there is 1.8 times increases chances of reducing crime rate. This is in line with Cobb Douglas production function theory. Also important to note is that policing practice of preventive include foot patrol, preventive patrol, problem oriented policing and team policing. The result can only be achieved when partners share information, investigating crimes, arresting and prosecuting criminals, gathering intelligence and acting on it before the crime is undertaken. Also noted is that police force should enhance confidence of the community at 63.1%, implying that when the trust goes up by 1% there is likelihood of community trusting the police with information 1.6 times which finally plays a role in reducing crime .

Keywords:- (Community Mobilization Strategies, Implementation of Community Policing.)

I. INTRODUCTION

Community policing is defined as a philosophy way of life and a proactive, decentralized approach designed to reduce crime, disorder and the fear of crime. Policing emphasizes full partnership between the community and its police in identifying and ameliorating local crime and disorder problems. The philosophy of community policing is built on the belief that people have a right to determine how

their communities is policed in order for them to exchange their involvement and support (Leoschut and Burton 2009)). It is not possible for police to effectively prevent and investigate crime without the willing participation of the public. Community policing therefore transforms the police from being an emergency squad in fighting crime into a proactive organization in participatory (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics 2015)).

This concept community policing was popularized in the United States of America and the United Kingdom from the 1980s and was based on the principle of coordination and participatory. Its origin is from two American scholars named James Wilson and George Kelling. Secondly, the concept is often said to have its origins in an article by In Sub-Saharan Africa, South Africa pioneered in implementation of community policing (Regoli. Hewitt & Maras 2013).

In Kenya, since the formation of the Police force, the Kenya Police Service has negated the awaited aspect of community policing derailing cordial relations with citizens. The police practice in Kenya has been seen by the public as a means of maintaining order while representing the interests of some dominant groups or individuals. This concept community policing has grown in popularity in Kenya through the Kenya Human Rights Commission and the Nairobi Central Business District Association (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics 2015) .However, the practice in Kenya started in May 2001 in Kibera, Ziwani, and Isiolo through joint collaboration between Vera, the Kenya Police, UN-Habitat, 'Safer world' and Nairobi Central Business District Association. The units have further been supported by the development of a national manual that is used in training communities at different sites in line with the police service,(Kenya National Bureau of Statistics 2015).

➤ Statement of problem

The crime in Kenya has been in existence since the post-independence era and has been gradually increasing as the urban population continues to rise at a faster pace than rural areas leading to rural urban migration. The government has adopted different approaches and strategies to counter the ever rising incidences of crime in major urban centres. Cities, towns, estates and villages in Kenya have recently been hit by a wave of violence, with insecurity accounts ranging from organized terror gangs, to violent robbery, abductions, poaching, cattle rustling, terrorism and murders. Despite measures such as rehabilitation and employment creation, the problem of crime and criminal activities continue to foster in the social fabric of the urban areas. If this pattern is left to continue, there may be high crime rate and hence the need to mobilize the community to enhance partnership. This

research is aimed at determining the influence of community mobilization strategy on implementation of community policing in Kenya.

➤ *Purpose of study*

The purpose of the study was to determine the effects of community mobilisation strategies on implementation of community policing

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Mobilisation of priorities and implementation of community policing*

Community mobilisation plays an important role in crime analysis today. This is not a new concept, but it enjoyed a revival as a result of information technology and the potential for geographical information surveys (Boba Santos, 2005). The model can predict future hotspots of crime (Groff and LaVigne, 2002). Community mobilisation facilitating visual and statistical analysis of the spatial nature of crime and other types of events, by allowing the analysts to link data sources together based on common variables. It provides plots that communicate results (Boba Santos, 2005). Crime sketch out has a long history which centre around inter-connection incidences of urban offence with sociological factors such as ethnic differences, education, social efficacy and cohesion and the meaning of the environmental factors in the context of offence.

By focusing on societies in transition, Mercy Corps (2009) is often working in conflict-affected contexts and those undergoing significant socio-economic change. Community mobilization efforts must take conflict dynamics and even positive tensions into account. Dialogue and transparency promote a certain degree of confidence and reduce friction. However, care must be taken to mitigate the potential negative impacts of all community mobilization activities. These are the main points of the “Do No Harm” concept and apply to all communities. It is Mercy Corps’ responsibility to avoid the pitfalls of jealousy and competition over scarce resources within communities, which can happen when aid or development opportunities are not carefully planned and communicated. By focusing on societies in transition, Mercy Corps is often working in conflict-affected contexts and those undergoing significant socio-economic change. Community mobilization efforts must take conflict dynamics and even positive tensions into account. Which projects can best build on connections across communities instead of fuelling tensions? How does a project impact perceptions of disparity and access? What precautions do we need to take, dialogue and transparency promote a certain degree of confidence and reduce friction. However, care must be taken to mitigate the potential negative impacts of all community mobilization activities. These are the main points of the “Do No Harm” concept and apply to all communities. It is a responsibility to avoid the pitfalls of jealousy and competition over scarce resources within communities, which can happen when aid or development opportunities are not carefully planned and communicated.(Mercy Corps 2009)

With community mobilization, participation is about meeting the interests of the whole community. When every member of a community has the chance, directly or through representation, to participate in the design, implementation and monitoring of community-level initiatives, there is a higher likelihood that the program accurately reflects their real needs and interests (Trapnell, Jenkins and Chêne 2017). The approach takes into consideration the different experiences, needs and capabilities of various groups in a community – women and men, youth and the elderly, persons with disabilities and the able-bodied, ethnic/religious/language minorities and majorities. Rather than “passive participation,” we aim to inspire “self-mobilization”, where communities organize and take initiative independent of any external actors.(Mercy Corps 2009)

According to UNODC,(2010),Crime data, including delineate, is closely connected to the creation of targeted prevention strategies. Kenya has a chronicle of a reactive, penal and politicized approach to policing with little emphasis on nip in the bud strategies, nor partnership with non-security agencies to tackle crime. However, in addition to conditional form from a human-rights standpoint, there is much evidence to support the cost-effectiveness of prevention .The information that is kept using the taxpayer money is to deal with the crime in a very effective way that profits the society therefore it is important to rethink of the strategies of mobilisation.

According to Mkutu *et al* (2015) creation of local crime alertness programs within the neighbourhood makes applications of group mobilization strategies in prevention crime at local household, schools visits, sports and music events, all seek to establish closer relations between police and members of the community.According to Lindekilde, Lasse (2014) considered risk of committing crime and agreed that it ruins society in many facets. The advent of community mobilization should be understood not only as a quest for more effective and accountable policing, but also as part of a wider public sector reform movement (Trapnell *et al* 2017)

According to Mkutu, Wandera, and Obondo (2015) states that commentators far to argue that community policing is transposed homeland security, maintaining that the two tendencies are together referred to as intelligence gathering, however it requires a close relationships with the public (Wisler, Onwudiwe 2019). Stability and community togetherness should achieve some degree of political stability and split values (Naudé, prinsloo and ladikos 2006) . Police outreach should too collaborate with community, however a period of political turmoil and the society is still driven by factionalism (Dupont 2007).Many studies agreed that neighbourhood watch or in other term referred as nyumba kumi community policing strategy had effect on curbing crime in Kenya.

According to Regoli,, Hewitt,and Maras (2013) community should also assure that the particular prevention method will have the desired results, and specify how the

results will be measured. Neighbourhood watch and citizen patrols are among the most common forms of community mobilization for crime prevention, Evaluation evidence suggests that such programs have a negligible effect on neighbourhood crime, resident fear of crime, and social cohesion ,Cramer, Christopher (2011) . Mobilization efforts linked to a broader vision of community safety and well-being require comprehensive planning and resources to implement as well as patience Community capacity has been defined in this article as the community’s relative ability to undertake collective action (Hesseling, 1995).

III. RESULT FINDING

Table 1.1 : The rate of return

Questionnaires	Frequency	Percentage %
Returned	98	98
Not returned	2	2
Total	100	100

From the table 100 questionnaires were administered to the interviewees, out of the total 98 questionnaires were returned. This translates to 98% return rate .According to Orodho (2009) a 70 percent return rate is sufficient.

1.2. Involvement in planning

The question sought to establish how often the community is involved in planning community policing practices. The results are shown in table 1.2

Table 2.1 : Community involvement in Policing Practices

Item	Frequency	percentage
Strongly agree	4	4
Agree	10	10
Undecided	2	2
Disagree	30	31
Strongly disagree	52	53
Total	98	100.00

The table above indicates that 52(53%) stated that community are never involved in policing by strongly disagreeing , followed by 30(31%) who also disagreed that community policing is engaging, this was followed by 10(10%) who attested that the police has been involving community effectively in policing, 4(4%) of the respondents were very clear and strongly disagreed and finally 2(2%) refused to answer the question.The implication of these results is that more need to be done by engage the community to embrace community policing.

Table 1.5 : Regression Coefficients of Community Mobilisation strategies on implementation of CP

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.231	.191		.000	.853	1.608
	Community mobilisation strategies	.600	.062	.642	9.700	.000	.477

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Community Mobilisation Strategies Program

$Y = \alpha + \beta X_4 + \epsilon$, where Y= Implementation of Community Mobilisation strategy Out come ; X_4 = Community Mobilisation Strategies . $Y = 1.231 + 0.600X_4 + \epsilon$.

Table 1.3 ANOVA of Logical Framework approach on implementation of CMS

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	3.245	1	3.245	93.089	.000 ^b
	Residual	7.045	134	.845		
	Total	10.290	135			
a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Community Mobilisation Strategies						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Logical Framework Approach						

From the ANOVA output shown in Table 1.3, it is evident that the community engagement , training and community/Police patrol are Community Mobilisation Strategies which are indeed a significant predictor of implementation of Community policing $F(1, 134) = 93.089$, $p = .000 < .05$. This means that community Mobilisation Strategies can be used to significantly predict the level of implementation of Community policing.

Table 1.4: Confidence between the police and the community

Scale of measurement	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	48	49
Disagree	14	14.3
Undecided	0	0
Agree	36	36.7
Strongly agree	0	0
Total	98	100

Table 1.4 reveals that a large proportion of the respondents 48 (49%) agreed with the statement that there is no confidence between the police and the community, this is followed by 36(36.7) agreed that there is confidence between the two groups 14 (14.3 %) disagreed that confidence exist between the community and the police , majority when interrogated further reveal that any information revealed to the police always finds its way back to the community .This makes it difficult for the community to trust the police. The study is in agreement with (Wisler & Onwudiwe, 2009) who found that Community mobilization may focus more on local-based initiatives, but it is also directly related to higher-level accountability and secret orientation, such as civilian police boards or watchdog agencies

From the analysis, there is a statistically significant positive unstandardized co-efficient of 0.600 within a 95% C.I (0.477, 0.722) as indicated by the coefficient matrix. Given that there is a significant p -value ($t = 9.700$; $p < .05$) of the unstandardized co-efficient value, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis ($\beta_4 = 0$). Hence, the alternative hypothesis ($\beta_4 \neq 0$) was supported and it was concluded that Community Mobilisation Strategies & Implementation of Community Policing has statistically significant influence on Each other.. This suggests that there is a 95% confidence that the true mean of improvement of implementation of Community Policing Program for every one-unit of Mobilisation strategies & Community policing of (0.477, 0.722) units. The Practice by one standard deviation results into an improvement in implementation of Community policing Program by 0.642 standard deviations.

1.6: Sharing of community based intelligence

The researcher sought to establish the extent to which sharing of community based intelligence helps in crime detection in the area. The findings are shown in table 1.6

Table 1.6: Sharing of community based intelligence

Scale of measurement	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	30	30.6
Disagree	20	20.4
Undecided	0	00.00
Agree	0	00.00
Strongly agree	48	49.00
Total	98	100.00

Table 1.6 revealed that a large proportion of the respondents 48 (49%) agreed with the statement that community based intelligence sharing with the police is ideal. 20(20.4%) of the respondents disagreed that community share intelligence with the police while 48(49.00%) of the respondents strongly disagreed. The majority number of participants agreed that Community sharing intelligence would be ideal in curbing crime . The study is in agreement with (Torjman, 2007) who found Experience showed successful mobilization processes need to be contextually relevant, sensitive to the vision and priorities of the community . It is important to build a flexibility and capacity to assess, respond and adapt to the evolving nature of community interests and change. Careful and continual assessment of local conditions, motivations and capacities, and achievable results is required.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

From the above findings the study concluded that there is need to formulate a clear way of reporting crime that is known to the community in an anonymous manner to reduce the sensitive information about crime falling back to the society. To gain more confidence of the community , the study proposes co-ordinated team of police and community approach in solving . However, police and community forums to discuss crime issues be a partnership.

The findings also revealed that majority of those who participate in crime ,finds it as a solution to there long struggle poverty solution. The conclusion is that poverty is a key cause of crime and leads to drug abuse as an impetus of engaging in Criminal activities . This means poverty can lead to most of the crimes and without basic needs, women and children are the most affected group in the community.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

Based on the major findings of the study, the following are recommended.

There is need for the Government to formulate a policy which allows at least a member of the household to be able to provide basic needs to the community. Secondly, there is need to train at least a member for trust to be created between the police and the community which will enhance crime reduction. However, police and community forums should be encouraged .

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